

In The Gates of New Physics - 8 Theory

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April 27, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the questions 8-theory answered up to this day, from coupling constants to families and dark energy, a new set of fundamental questions now is solved. Those questions are oriented toward the why things are the way they are. The 8- Theory allows us a glimpse into space travel and matric deformations, physics of variations, physics oriented toward complete simplicity and dynamic probabilistic framework.

Motion versus Variation

Up until now, we have asked how we can describe the motion. From now, we can ask how we can describe the metric variation. The 8-theory equations regard particles as arbitrary variations of a manifold, and contains only the manifold in her equations. The fermions and bosons are subject of secondary importance, just as in QFT those are regarded as excitements of the field. The advantage is that now, we do not need to use any operators of Creation and destruction, such things happens in natural and spontaneous fashion. That is given by the first equation. In terms of notation, we can attain a major simplification, as those do not need more than one Equation or even one term.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad - \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} &= 0 \\ \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' &= 0 \quad (1) \\ \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i &= 0 \quad (1.1) \end{aligned}$$

No need of frames of reference

Second major simplification is the need for describing physics from different frames of reference. That is the innate appearance of spatial dimensions within our framework. Such things than requires additional complexities such as field transformations and coordinate transformations, groups and so on. The equations of the 8-theory does not have any spatial dimensions. That is a second major advantage. All that theory deals with and cares about is a manifold. A Lorentz manifold. Such questions on frames of reference are not important in this level of description; it is more fundamental view than such relativistic questions. **The manifold vary, that is all it does.** That is the ultimate idea. Those variations yield fermions and net variations than propagate bosons from those fermions. What those fermions find out about the speed of light is than a higher level set of questions, given to us by Lorentz and Einstein.

Physics of what versus the physics of why.

Up until now, if we can overview the entire framework of physics by asking questions of the sort of what. What is the motion, what is the probability, what is the cross section, what is the energy? What is the frequency? The language is long and complicated; it includes four vectors, propagators, partial differential equations and many other disciplines. None gives us a more fundamental view on why. Why those magnitudes? Why does bosons have that spin and fermions the other? Why does fermions anti- commute and bosons do commute. Why four forces or why only three families?

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (2.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ...$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

Those questions are all attainable within our new framework. Which is nature eliminating the variations or curvature in an endless succession. Net curvature is bosons manifested. Curvature converging inward is mass. There are infinite bosons, one for each prime. There are infinite families forming below first generation and their mass converging to zero. We predicted a forth family forming below first, which total elements mass, is 0.113 Mev . About 56 times lighter than first family. The equation of the mass series has two variations:

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{i=1}^r N_E} * \frac{1}{9} \quad (5)$$

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$$N_E = 2E; E \geq 1$$

Space travel

Up until now, we analyzed the distance as a linear function. We believed we need to cross the entire metric to reach a distant location. The new framework we obtained allows us to travel in space via compact topological spaces, which stay as they are over time and cover the entire space. That is given to us by the forth term in the first equation.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad - \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial t} = 0$$

The condition is to reach the maximal amount of energy, or curvature, than we can shift from the metric space to the underline topological space and then an additional resifting to our final destination. The shifting can be instantaneous or continuous. Either direct jump or blazing the metric to the topology and then the opposite. We require this condition to hold true so the manifold will be stationary, and no data available from the first three terms.

$$ST: M_{x1,y1,z1} \rightarrow M_{x2,y2,z2} \quad (7)$$

$$8T: M_{x1,y1,z1} \rightarrow g \quad (8)$$

$$8T^{-1}: g \rightarrow M_{x2,y2,z2} \quad (9)$$

Simplicity versus complexity

The major feature of a fundamental theory of physics should be simplicity. Simplicity in the Amount of both words and ideas needed to be described, in the equations themselves, their amount and their very own nature. Such great simplicity, which will allow us to include as much as we know about the World within it. To explain everything, with almost nothing. That is the ultimate purpose of the final theory. Just like Einstein did with General relativity and Maxwell in electricity. The 8-theory allows us to do just that concerning almost all the unanswered questions left in physics. From life to Dark energy, from couplings to families, all we need is those equations:

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (3)$$

$$M_{n+1} = \frac{M_n + (7)}{7 * \prod_{l=1}^r N(E)} \quad (5)$$

$$M_{n+1} = \frac{M_n + (7)}{7 * \prod_{l=1}^r N(E)} * \left(\frac{1}{9} \right) \quad (6)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. 8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)